

Examine the staff training and development culture of public universities in Ghana and its impacts on employee retention

William Aryee Armah

Registry Department

Ghana Communication Technology University, Ghana

Abstract: *The study examined the relationship between training and development and employee retention in some selected public universities in Ghana. Public universities in Ghana are faced with myriad of problems related to training and development and employee retention. For instance, ninety-seven percent of public universities in the country do not allow employees to have required external training or developmental training. In fact, if an employee develops a personal ambition for further training or self-development; the public universities would rather he/she tendered a resignation before he or she embarks on such developmental studies. In a style of a qualitative research, descriptive-casual survey method was adopted. Data were collected from the administration of questionnaire and were analysed using multiple regression analysis. Findings show that training and development has a positive relationship with employee retention. This means that a positive relationship exists between training & development and employees' retention. It implies that the more the training and development of the bank employees, the higher the chances of the employees' being retained. This implies that training and development has significant effect on employee retention. The research recommends that a dissatisfied employee cannot work effectively to achieve the organizational goals.*

Keywords: *Employee, Employee motivation, Employee retention, Training and Development.*

I. Background to the Study

Human resources constitute a very critical ingredient for the attainment of organisational goals. According to Taher and Arifen (2000), with time the importance of the human factor in the realisation and attainment of organisational goals has increased considerably because of increasing competition and globalization of management. Robyn (2012) further states that the strength of an institution lies in its human capital and that it is therefore important to align human resource policies and procedures to attract and retain skilled employees. In this vein, organizations around the globe are vigorously competing for the best employees to achieve their organisational goals (Mahmud & Idrish, 2011). Realizing the critical role that human resources play in organizations, employee retention remains very critical to the long-term health and success of business organizations (Guest, Michia, Conway & Sheanan, 2003; Rombaut & Guerry, 2019).

Due to the dynamic and competitive nature of the tertiary sector environment, an innovative human resource development practices have to focus on equipping employees with new and diverse skills, and also to ensure flexibility of employees so as to be able to respond to the current changes. Human resource development practices need to consciously turn around issues that not only enhance job security but make the employee satisfied on the job with increased job security and satisfaction (Barrows & Wesson, 2000). This derives from the fact that the best asset in an organization are the people, and not just people, skilled and competent people who need to be managed effectively to ensure job satisfaction and retention. However, the situation in the

Ghanaian tertiary sector has potentials for high attrition rate due to poor human resource development practices and employee retention: evidence from the Ghanaian tertiary sector is lack of job security and satisfaction occasioned by adjustments in the salary. There have been many justifiable factors that affect retention, such as company image, learning opportunities, performance recognition and rewards, job security, fair pay, training and development and working conditions (Abraham & Medoff, 1984). The retention policy involves strategies put in place to make employees comfortable at work so as to improve their job satisfaction to enable the workforce remain in that organization (Abraham & Medoff, 1985). Any other practice otherwise would reduce the satisfaction of employees.

The importance of human resources in an organization can be well perceived in the fact that factors of production including land and capital cannot translate themselves into economic outputs unless with the coordinated efforts of men. This view is shared by Psacharopoulos and Woodhall (1997) who assert that human resources constitute the ultimate basis of the wealth of nations; capital and national resources are passive factors of production but human beings are the active agencies who accumulate capital, exploit national resources, build social, economic and political organization and carry on national development.

Human Resource Development is seen as a process of acquiring and increasing the number of persons who have the skills, education and experience which are critical for the economic growth of the country (Harbison, 1962). In addition, a discourse on human resource development practices in the tertiary sector is about investing in improving the skills, innovation and technical capability of the workforce with the target of improved productivity and employee retention. It can be arguably said that the concept of training and development practices not restricted to workers alone but extends to the employers because they too need to sharpen their innate resources for more efficiency and effectiveness in the management of physical and other human resources.

Today's economic operations, especially of public universities, are knowledge-based, and for a bank to meet the challenge of dynamism of business and the ever-growing global interconnectivity of tertiary sector operations, great attention should be paid to training and development. Meeting the N25billion recapitalization by public universities, construction of captivating structures, and acquisition of modern physical assets cannot, in themselves, translate to operational success, unless with the competences, skills and creativity of the available human resources. This of course is an x-ray of the significance of human resource development practices.

The main ingredients that make up the qualities of human resource development practices as identified by various authors and researchers. These include; quality education, training and development, fair pay, good working condition and good health (Oluwatobi & Ogunrinola, 2011; Odusola, 1998; Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 1995; Becker 1993; Okadara, 1978). Becker's (1993) perspective for instance, modern economists seem to concur that education and health care are the key to improving human resource and ultimately increasing the economic outputs of the nation. Atagana (2011) however, widens the scope of human resource development to include investment in education, training, health as well as investment in all social services which influence man's productive capacities, especially transport facilities and housing. It is so considered for the fact that efficient management of the earlier mentioned resource elements cited in this work will go a long way to enhance economic growth of a country.

The paper, here, therefore, investigates the effect of training and development on employee retention in public universities in Ghana. In order to achieve these research objectives the paper exhaustively reviews literatures on training and development and employee retention.

1.1 Statement of Problem

The problem of this study originated from the fact that public universities in Ghana are faced with myriad of problems related to training and development and employee retention. For instance, ninety-seven percent of public universities in the country do not allow employees to have required external training or developmental training. In fact, if an employee develops a personal ambition for further training or self-development; the public universities would rather he/she tendered a resignation before he or she embarks on such developmental studies. That is why employees hardly stay for a long time in the public universities, once they find any opportunity that is better they switch immediately.

1.2 Research Question

The question raised for this study was to assess the effect of training and development on employee retention in Ghana Public universities.

1.2.1 Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to examine the effect of training and development on employee retention in Ghana Public universities.

1.2.2 Hypothesis

- H₀** There is no significant relation between training and development and employee retention in Ghana Public universities.
- H₁** There is a significant relation between training and development and employee retention in Ghana Public universities.

II. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Frame Work

2.1.1 Employee Retention

Employee retention can be defined as the policies and practices organizations use to avoid precious employees from quitting their jobs. However, Ben-Bakr, Al-Shammari, Jefri and Prasad (1994) argued that organizations can avoid business instability when talented employees are retained. Retention can be seen as the ability to hold onto those employees you want to keep, for longer than your competitors (Johnson, 2002, cited in Shaibu, Noor, Tirmizi Bashir, 2009). Again, Denton (2000) puts forward the view about employee retention that employees who are contented and satisfied with their jobs are more devoted towards their job and always put their effort to progress their organizational customers' satisfaction.

Researchers such as Taplin, Winterton, and Winterton (2005), Amadasu (2003) and Gberebie (2003) have established in their studies that, employees will surely stay and work for the flourishing and accomplishment of organizational goals if suitable employee retention strategies are adopted and implemented by organizations. In addition, Action and Golden (2003) state that retention of employees is not only important but retention of valued skills is more important. According to the researchers, human resource department plays the dynamic role for retention of employees.

Freyermuth (2007) commented that retention starts with the recruiting of correct individuals and continues with practicing program to keep them engaged and committed to the organization. According to him, it is considered as multifaceted component of an organization resource policies. Baker (2006) said that employee retention is

very important as because of the fact that hiring new employees are far complicated as well as costlier than to remain with the present employees in the organization.

However, Olowu and Adamolekum (2005), stated that because of the need for effective and efficient delivery of goods and services by organizations in public or private sector, it is becoming more essential to secure and manage competent human resource as the most valuable resource of any organization.

Gberebie (2008) has assured that employee retention implementation strategies is very important. In addition, employee retention strategies refers to the strategy and means and a set of decision making behaviour put formulated by organizations to retain their competent workforce for performance.

2.2 Training and Development

Training and development is an important variable for employee retention (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Solomon, 1992; Snell & Dean, 1992; Arthur, 1994; Snell & Youndt, 1995; Mac Duffie, 1995; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Ichniowski, Shaw & Prensushi, 1997; Cappeli, 2000; Cole, 2000). Performance of particular work exclusive of a particular organization and that a worker becomes needed only to that organization. An employee who happens to be in this state of affair becomes more committed and wanting to work for life in the organization (Brenya, 2014). Still, training and development such job security requires a certain degree of reciprocity: a company that systematically trains and develops its employees develops their market value more favourably (Felicity, Eric & David, 2013). This increases employees' productivity, commitment and reduces turnover. Companies may also assist their employees in career planning. In doing so, companies encourage employees to take more responsibility for their own development, including the development of skills viewed as significant in the company (Doyle, 1997).

Barringer, Jones, and Neubaum (2005) compared rapid-growth and slow growth firms and found that rapid growth firms depends heavily on the abilities and efforts of their employees to maintain their growth oriented strategies. The fast-growth firms used training programs to achieve their objectives and emphasize employee development to a significantly greater extent than their slow growth counter parts. Therefore, training and employee development practices are more common in rapid growth firms than slow growth ones. Miller (2006) examined the growth strategies in the retail sector and suggested that modern retailer should place more emphasis on the policies and practices that could contribute to staff retention, rather than on the immediacy of recruitment and selection. Zhao (2004) reviewed the change in the area of human resource development in Japan and observed that some companies and industries have shifted towards a more strategic approach that emphasizes the impact of effective learning at both individual and organizational levels on long-term organizational competitiveness. Huselid (1995) found that the education and development of employees have a significant effect both upon the personnel productivity and the short-term and long-term indicators of organizational performance.

Ngo, Turban, Lau, & Lui (1998) investigated the effect of country origin on human capital development practices of firms from the United States, Great Britain, Japan and Hong Kong operating in Hong Kong. The study results showed that structural training and development and retention-oriented fair pay were related to various measures of firm performance. Interestingly, Paul and Anantharaman (2003) in searching the links between human capital development and organization performance, proposed that career development programmes demonstrate a true interest of the organization for the growth of its personnel, which in turn stimulates commitment, devotion and retention, which subsequently raises personnel productivity and consequently economic output.

Cerio (2003) examined the manufacturing in Spain and found that quality management practices related to product design and development, and human resource practices, are the most significant predictors of operational performance. Michie and Quinn (2001) investigated the relationship between UK firm's use of flexible work practices and corporate performance and suggested that low levels of training are negatively correlated with corporate performance.

In a US Department of Labour (1993) study of high performance work practices, it was found that the use of formal training programs was associated with significantly higher productivity growth. Becker and Huselid (1999) argue that the economic returns of extensive training are more likely to be captured by the firm if employees are motivated to stay and contribute to the firm's success fostered in part by selective hiring competitive pay packages and team-oriented work environments. In addition, Youndt et al (1996) theorize that human capital development practices designed to develop talented and team-oriented workers improve employee productivity and employee retention.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Herzberg Two-Factor Theory

One of the earliest researches in the area of employee retention that affected motivation was Frederick Herzberg work (Herzberg, Mausner & Synderman, 1959). Herzberg and his associates began their initial work on factors affecting work motivation in the mid-1950s. Their first effort entitled a "thorough review of existing research" to that date on the subject (Herzberg et al., 1959). Based on the review, Herzberg carried out his now famous survey of 200 accountants and engineers from whom he derived the initial frame work for his theory of motivation. The theory, as well as the supporting data was first published in 1959 (Herzberg et al., 1959) and was subsequently amplified and developed in a later book (Herzberg, 1966). Based on his survey, Herzberg discovered that employees tended to describe satisfying experiences in terms of factors that were intrinsic to the content of the job itself. These factors were called "motivators" and concluded such variables as achievement, recognition, the work itself, responsibility, advancement and personal growth. Conversely, dissatisfying experiences, called "hygiene" factors, largely resulted from extrinsic, non-job-related factors, such as company policies and administration, salary, coworker relations, and supervisory styles, job security, personal life, work condition and status (Steers & Porter, 1983). Herzberg argued based on these results that eliminating the causes of dissatisfaction (through hygiene factors) would not result in a state of satisfaction. Instead, it would result in a neutral state. Satisfaction (and motivation) would occur only as a result of the use of motivators (Herzberg, 1966).

The implications of this theory of employee motivation are clear: motivation can be increased through basic changes in the nature of an employee's job, that is, through job enrichment (Steers & Porter, 1983). Thus, jobs should be redesigned to allow for increased challenge and responsibility, opportunities for advancement, and personal growth, and recognition.

According to Herzberg (1966), the "factors leading to job satisfaction are separate and distinct from those, that lead to job dissatisfaction." Therefore, managers who seek to eliminate factors that create job dissatisfaction can bring about peace, but not necessarily motivation. They will be placating their work force rather than motivating them to stay for life (Robins, 1993). Kreitner and Kinicki (1998) highlight one of Herzberg's findings, where managers rather than giving employees additional tasks of similar difficulty (horizontal loading), "vertically loading" consists of giving workers more responsibility. This is where employees take on tasks normally performed by their supervisors. In essence, there are more to a manager's role in motivating employees other than compensation, good working conditions, and similar factors. Herzberg argued that for an employee to be

truly motivated, the employee's job has to be fully enriched where the employee has the opportunity for achievement and recognition, stimulation, responsibility, and advancement.

Although, Herzberg's theory was generally accepted, there are some criticisms that it applies least to people with largely unskilled jobs or those whose work are interesting, repetitive, monotonous and limited in scope. He was also accused of assuming a correlation between satisfaction and productivity through his research stressed satisfaction and ignored productivity. Recent research indicates that employee satisfaction does not necessarily contribute directly to productivity. Satisfaction may be viewed as a passive attribute, while more proactive measures such as motivation levels are viewed as more closely linked to behavioural changes and performance (Hayday, 2003).

In as much as some behavioural scientists agree with Herzberg that employees are well motivated when the motivator factors are achieved. Other schools of thought share different opinion. Some behavioural scientist also argue that there is more to motivating employees and getting them satisfied than just the motivator factors enumerated by Herzberg. On another interesting note, some behavioural scientists have sought to invalidate Frederick Herzberg's, motivation-hygiene factors claiming it lacks empirical support. One of such scientist is King (2005). In his book; 'clarification and evaluation of the two-factor theory', which appeared in the psychological bulletin, he sought to explicate and evaluate five distinct versions of the two-factor theory of job satisfaction. He concluded that two of these versions are invalid, as they are not supported by any empirical studies.

A criticism levelled against Herzberg's theory suggesting that Herzberg's original formulation of the model may have been a methodological artifact. It was further explained that, the theory does not consider individual differences, conversely predicting all employees will react in an identical manner to changes in motivating-hygiene factors. Furthermore, concern was raised, that Herzberg's theory did not specify how motivation and hygiene factors are to be measured (Hackman & Oldman, 1976). While some behavioural scientist raised issues with the critical incident technique used by Herzberg in collecting data as appropriate, others like Bellot and Tutor (1990) had problems with the type of employees used. According to a research study conducted by Tutor in 1986 with Tennessee Career Ladder Program (TCLP), they concluded that not all employees are motivated by Herzberg's 'motivator needs' and that, teachers especially were more motivated by hygiene needs like money. They criticized Herzberg for using employees from only industrial sector. For the purpose of this study, the Herzberg two-factor theory has been applied. The reason being that the variable used in the work is embedded in Herzberg's theory. Therefore, public universities should choose any of the factors that best suit an employee in order to reduce the rate of employee turnover in the tertiary sector.

2.4 Empirical Review

2.4.1 Training and Development and Employee Retention

Research conducted by different scholars' state that training and development are factors that play very important role in employee retention (Meyer & Allen, 1992; Solomon, 1992; Snell & Dean, 1992; Arthur, 1994; Snell & Youndt, 1992; Macdiffe, 1995; Delanet and Huselid, 1996; Ichniowski et al., 1997; Cappelli, 2000; Cole, 2000; Cited in Muhammad, 1997). According to them, these variables can help to reduce absenteeism and better quality –work. Messmer (2000) found that one of the important factors in employee retention is investment on employee training and development. Fitz-enz (1990) also found that training and development, is a factor responsible for employees retention. Organization always invests in the form of training and development on those workers from whom they expect to return and give output on its investment.

Tomlinson (2002) forwarded the view that organizations can keep the leading edge in this competitive world by having their employees well trained in the latest technologies. Grag and Rastogi (2006), explained that in today's

competitive environment, feedback is very essential for organizations from employees and the more knowledge the employee acquires, the more he or she will perform and meet the global challenges of the market place. Handy (2001) has mentioned that proper innovation, and assimilation of new knowledge is essential for survival in any work environment. Thus knowledge is the most expensive asset of any firm. Walker (2001) stated in his study that training and development is one of the important retention programs to retain the employees

III. Methodology

The research examines the effect of training and development on employee retention in some selected public universities in Bauchi. The research design used for this study is the survey method (Descriptive-Casual survey method). Questionnaires were used in collecting data from the public universities while the top and middle level staff of the public universities formed the population of the study. The primary data is basically from the administration of questionnaires. This is conducted with the focus population of the research work, that is, the top and middle level staff in Public universities in Ghana. In order to examine the effect of training and development on Employee Retention in public universities in Ghana, the following simple regression model stated below was used to test the hypothesis:

$$ER_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TD_i + U_i$$

Where

ER = Employee retention

TD = Training and Development

U= error term

Analysis and Results

Table 1: Reliability Test Result

S/N	Questionnaire	Cronbach	Number of	Remark
		Alpha	Items	
		Reliability		
		Result		
	Questionnaire Instrument	0.770	7	Very
				Reliable

Source: SPSS 22.0 Output

Table 1 shows the result of the reliability test of the research instrument. The result shows that the instrument is very reliable.

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Training and Development and employee retention

S/N	Variable	Scale (x)	Frequency (f)	%
a.	Training and Development is considered			
	Strongly Disagree	1	46	23.4
	Disagree	2	10	5.1
	Undecided	3	6	3.0
				42.
	Agree	4	83	1
	Strongly Agree	5	52	26.4
	Total		197	100
b.	Employees are encouraged to share			
	training experiences			
	Strongly Disagree	1	3	1.5
	Disagree	2	49	24.9
	Undecided	3	16	8.1
				33.
	Agree	4	66	5
	Strongly Agree	5	63	32.0
	Total		197	100
c.	Continue to work for the organization			
	since they permit further education			
	Strongly Disagree	1	12	6.1
	Disagree	2	19	9.6
	Undecided	3	86	43.7
	Agree	4	55	27.9
				12.
	Strongly Agree	5	25	7
	Total		197	100

Sources: Survey Data (2022)

The result in table 2 seeks to find out the extent of training and development and employee retention. It shows that majority of the respondents agree (83 or 42.1%), agree (66 or 33.5%) and undecided (86 or 43.7%) agreed that training and development is considered as focal point in employee retention, second the respondents agree that employees are encouraged to share training experiences and they are undecided on whether or not to continue work for the organization since they permit further education. Hence, it is concluded that training and development has influence on employees' retention.

3.2 Model Summary

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin - Watson
1	.265 ^a	.070	.039	.51991	1.976

Source: (Author, 2022)

Table 3 shows the value of the correlation coefficient and the R-squared. The correlation value shows the effect of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The value of the *R*, 0.265 which is 26.5% shows that there is weak relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The value of the coefficient of determination R^2 , 0.070, which is 7% indicated that the training and development contributes to employee retention with only 7%. Since the value of Durbin-Watson is approximately 2, the result indicated that there is no autocorrelation.

Table 4: ANOVA

Mode		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.748	7	.535	2.044	.052 ^p
	Residual	49.516	189	.262		
	Total	53.264	196			

Source: (Author, 2022)

Table 4 shows the result of the F- test with a value of 2.044 and p-value of 0.052. This shows that there is a strong linear dependency existing among the variables, since the P-value is less than 0.10. It indicates that the regression model is a good fit for determining the effect of training and development on employees' retention among public universities in Ghana.

Regression Result

Table 5 Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	2.301	.418		5.510	.000		
	TD	.145	.060	.200	2.436	.016	.733	1.365

a. Dependent Variable: ER

- (ii) The findings equally shows paucity of recent studies on employee retention. Public universities in Ghana should therefore strengthen their research and development department to provide capacity enhancement and development of staff.
- (iii) The study recommended that, public universities should discourage outsourcing in their system. The use of contract and outsourced staff for the purpose of building a strong trust mechanism should be discouraged. The contract or outsourced staff provide cheap labour. Cheap labour could affect the level of trust and trust when undermined could create room for dishonest practices and fraud which inevitably leads to bank collapse.

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